

A novel hierarchical “ceramic in polymer - polymer in ceramic” structure composite solid-state electrolyte for safer lithium ion batteries

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Abstract

The development of advanced composite solid-state electrolytes (CSSEs) is considered to be one of the most promising solutions for technological breakthroughs in lithium ion batteries (LIBs). However, it is challenging to fabricate satisfied CSSEs that can meet requirements from mechanical, thermal, safety, and electrochemical perspectives at the same time. Herein, a novel CSSE with the “ceramic in polymer - polymer in ceramic (CIP-PIC)” hierarchical structure is introduced, which exhibits enhanced mechanical properties, safer thermal behavior, and better fire resistance compared to conventional Polyethylene oxide (PEO) solid-polymer electrolytes (SPEs). The fabricated PMC10 CSSE shows a crystallinity of 15.2%, a Young’s modulus of 3.1 MPa, and an optimal ionic conductivity of $2.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 50°C. The compatible interface enables assembled symmetrical Li cells stable plating/stripping galvanostatic cycles for 900 hours at 0.2 mA cm⁻². The LiFePO₄|PMC10|Li cell shows an initial capacity density of 158.5 Ah kg⁻¹, and a capacity retention of 80.3% after 200 cycles. More importantly, compared to PEO SPE, a reduction of 33.4% of the heat release capacity (HRC) verifies the enhanced fire safety performance of PMC10 CSSE. This work provides an effective approach for the development of CSSEs for the realization of fire-safer LIBs.

Keywords: Lithium-ion battery; solid-state electrolyte; fire safety; composite electrolyte

1. Introduction

To address the predicament posed by the depletion of fossil fuels, it is imperative to promote sustainable, green, and clean energy sources, such as solar and wind energy, as alternatives to traditional options. However, these alternative sources are inherently unstable, variable, and heavily reliant on mitigating the intermittency of renewable energy production[1-4]. In recent decades, the lithium-ion battery (LIB) has emerged as the most promising solution for affordable electrochemical energy storage and has asserted its dominance across the spectrum of electrical power applications ranging from telecommunications, hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) to electric vehicles (EVs) due to its exceptional energy density, rapid charging capability, and prolonged life cycle[5-9]. To achieve high dielectric constant and low viscosity, current commercial LIBs electrolytes typically include a mix of lithium salts and solvents, comprising cyclic carbonates and one or two linear carbonates[10]. While these combinations offer good electrochemical performance and cost-effectiveness, the flammable nature of organic solvents puts batteries at risk of thermal runaway, fire, and even explosion when subjected to mechanical, thermal, or electrical abuse[11-13].

Target to this, diverse approaches have been developed to reduce safety hazards either from the structural modification of components or from the advancement of thermal management aspects. Adding appropriate flame retardant (FR) additives was first proposed to reduce the flammability of both liquid and solid electrolytes. According to the mechanism and retardant elements, FR additives are categorized into four types: phosphorus additives, fluoride additives, ionic liquid additives, and composite additives[14-17]. Recently, metal-organic-frameworks (MOFs), such as HKUST-1, ZIF-67, and UiO-66 have been demonstrated to possess potential with proper flame retardancy[18-20]. Furthermore, various crystalline oxides have been introduced as

solid inorganic electrolytes (SIEs) for their higher conductivity and thermal stability, including garnet-types ($\text{Li}_{6.4}\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_{1.4}\text{Ta}_{0.6}\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZTO)), perovskite-types ($\text{Li}_{3x}\text{La}_{2/3-x}\text{TiO}_3$ (LLTO)), and sodium superionic conductor (NaSICON)-types ($\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Al}_x\text{Ge}_{2-x}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LAGP) and $\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Al}_x\text{Ti}_{2-x}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LATP))[21-23]. However, it remains a problem to create a favorable solid-solid interface to reduce the interfacial impedance for Li^+ conduction[24].

To break out the limitation associated with the single polymer or inorganic solid electrolyte, composite solid-state electrolytes (CSSEs) were defined and applied in numerous studies as they integrate the excellent flexibility of polymers and dendrite suppression capability of ceramics[25-29]. In previous work, Chen et al fabricated PEO/LLZTO CSSEs by adjusting the composite composition to achieve structure from “PIC” to “CIP”, where a high ionic conductivity of $\sim 10^{-4}$ S cm^{-1} at 55°C was obtained[30]; Huo et al designed a sandwich CSSE structure referred to as “CIP-PIC-CIP” by leveraging the size effect, which enabled stable plating/stripping cycling at the current density of 0.2 mA cm^{-2} for 400 hours[31]. Nevertheless, most works lack the consideration of fire safety evaluation for these modified CSSEs.

Herein, we construct a novel CSSE named PMC with a "CIP-PIC" bilayer structure, which is shown in Fig. 1. This special hierarchical structure is formed due to the gravity effect of ceramics during preparation and the distribution of layers can be adjusted flexibly. With this unique structure, PMCs show inhibited crystalline ability and improved mechanical properties. Since its compatible contact interface and crystallization inhibition effect, the bilayer CSSE modified with 10% LLZTO (PMC10) shows an optimal ionic conductivity of 2.33×10^{-4} S cm^{-1} at 50°C, stable plating/stripping galvanostatic cycles for 900 h under 0.2 mA cm^{-2} and a favorable capacity retention efficiency of 80.3% after 200 cycles. Moreover, PMC10 demonstrates a significant

enhancement in fire safety, as evidenced by a notable 33.4% reduction in heat release capacity (HRC).

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the hierarchical “CIP-PIC” PMC CSSEs for safer lithium-ion batteries.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials

Lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI, 99.8%), poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO, $M_w=600,000$), *N*-1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), and acetonitrile (99.5%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. Lithium foils, LiFePO_4 (LFP), poly (vinylidene difluoride) (PVDF), and carbon black (Super-P) were supplied by MTI chemical reagent company. $\text{Li}_{6.4}\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_{1.4}\text{Ta}_{0.6}\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZTO, $D_{50} = 450\text{-}550$ nm) was bought from Shenzhen Huaqing new material technology Co. Ltd (China). $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{BTC})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\cdot\text{Guest}$ (HKUST-1) was synthesized and activated as reported before[32].

2.2 Preparation of PMC solid-state electrolytes

Electrolyte membranes were prepared by the solution casting method. Briefly, 0.7 g PEO and 0.31 g LiTFSI ($\text{Li}^+:\text{EO} = 1:15$) were dispersed in acetonitrile and magnetically stirred overnight at room temperature to form a homogeneous solution, which was followed by adding 5 wt% activated HKUST-1 MOFs inside and stirring for another 2 h until evenly dispersed. Subsequently,

pre-milled LLZTO powder (10, 30, and 50 wt%) was added to the slurry and stirred overnight. The blend was finally cast onto a horizontal Teflon plate and volatilized for 48 h to remove most of the solvent, then continued to dry in a dynamic vacuum oven at 40°C for another 48 h to make solvents evaporate completely. Hence, these CSSE membranes with a thickness of ~150 μm could be obtained and abbreviated as PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50 separately. PMC membranes were cut into circles with a 16 mm-diameter hole punch and transferred into the Ar-filled glove box after final vacuum drying for 6 h. Three control groups (PEO, PM, and PC10) were fabricated by similar preparation procedures as shown in Table 1, where the PEO group means without any additives except for Li salt (distinguishes from the pure PEO, which is commercial polymeric products without any treatment); the PM group was obtained by adding same concentration of MOFs based on PEO group; PC10 group was prepared by adding 10 wt% of LLZTO based on PEO group.

Table 1 Composition of various solid electrolytes for LIBs.

Group	Electrolyte matrix	Modification
Pure PEO	PEO	-
PEO	PEO + LiTFSI	-
PM	PEO + LiTFSI	5 wt% MOF
PC10	PEO + LiTFSI	10 wt% LLZTO
PMC10	PEO + LiTFSI	5 wt% MOF + 10 wt% LLZTO
PMC30	PEO + LiTFSI	5 wt% MOF + 30 wt% LLZTO
PMC50	PEO + LiTFSI	5 wt% MOF +50 wt% LLZTO

2.3 Materials characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded using the PANalytical Empyrean with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) at room temperature. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was acquired in ATR mode with the Thermofisher Nicolet 5700 spectrometer ranging from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Morphological analyses and elemental mapping of samples were carried out by a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) instrument (Apreo 2S, ThermoFisher with 5 or 15 kV), the samples were sputtered with gold with a spraying time of 120 seconds and 40 mA. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was employed on TA Q200 with a ramp of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a nitrogen atmosphere within the temperature range of -90 to 150°C . Only the second heating round was collected to remove the thermal history. The crystallinity (χ_c) of PMC electrolyte was calculated regarding enthalpies (ΔH_m) of PEO perfect crystals as Eq. (1):

$$\chi_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_{PEO} * f_{PEO}} \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m and ΔH_{PEO} are the melting enthalpies of PMC electrolyte and PEO perfect crystals (213.7 J g^{-1}) respectively, while f_{PEO} is the weight fraction of PEO in PMC electrolytes[33]. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curves under nitrogen atmosphere were measured by using TA Q50 with a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ from ambient temperature to 800°C . The dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) was performed by TA Q800 in a multifrequency strain mode to access the mechanical characteristics of electrolytes with an initial static force of 1 mN and a ramp force of 0.1 N min^{-1} . Young's modulus is defined as the ratio of stress (σ) to strain (ε).

$$E = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\varepsilon$ and $\Delta\sigma$ are axial strain (proportional deformation) and tensile stress (force per unit area) in the linear elastic region of stress-strain curves. Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E''), and damping factor ($\tan \delta$) were recorded at temperatures ranging from -80 to 60°C , with a heating rate

of 3°C min⁻¹ under a frequency of 1 Hz and a preload of 0.1 N; the dimension of sample was 30 × 5 mm.

2.4 Electrochemical measurements

Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements were performed to examine the electrochemical window by using stainless steel (SS) as the working electrode and lithium metal as the counter electrode, with a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹ from 2.0 to 5.5 V vs Li/Li⁺. To determine the ionic conductivities (σ) of PMCs at different temperatures from 25 to 80°C, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was measured with a Biologic SP-200 potentiostat. The electrolyte membranes were squeezed between two pieces of SS for measuring the impedance within the frequency range of 0.1 to 10⁶ Hz and an alternative current (AC) potential amplitude of 10 mV. The relevant formula used to calculate the ionic conductivity is as follows:

$$\sigma = \frac{d}{A \cdot R_b} \quad (3)$$

where d , A , and R_b indicate the thickness of PMC membranes, the electrode contact area, and the resistance obtained from the corresponding Nyquist plot, separately. The activation energy of PMC electrolytes is calculated following the Arrhenius relation:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 * \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{kT}\right) \quad (4)$$

where σ_0 , E_a , k , and T are the pre-exponential factor, activation energy, Boltzmann constant, and Kelvin temperature, respectively. In the potential range of 2.5 to 4.0 V vs Li⁺/Li at 50°C, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was conducted with the Biologic SP-200 potentiostat at a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹.

Lithium stripping and plating experiments were performed to evaluate the interfacial stability of PMC electrolytes against Li metal. Li|PMC|Li symmetrical cells were fabricated and tested for galvanostatic cycles at a current density of 0.2 mA cm⁻² including 0.5 h stripping and 0.5 h plating

alternating steps at 50°C. In order to analyze the cycle life and rate capability, the cathode slurry was prepared by mixing LFP, PVDF, and Super P in NMP solvent at a mass ratio of 8:1:1, and the slurry was scraped onto aluminum foil using the doctor blade technique and dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C for 12 h. Afterward, the cathode sheets were cut into 13 mm discs and dried again at 110°C before being transferred to a glove box. Ultimately, a final loading of $\sim 2 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$ for the active material was obtained. CR2032-type coin cells were assembled in the Ar-filled glovebox with LFP cathodes, PMC electrolytes, and Li metal anodes for cycling tests. Galvanostatic charge/discharge tests were carried out using Neware BTS-4000 charge/discharge battery testers under 50°C within a potential window of 2.5 to 3.8 V vs Li/Li⁺ under various current densities, the specific current related to the 1C rate of LFP was assumed to be 170 mA g⁻¹.

2.5 Fire-safety evaluation

To investigate the flame-retardant effect of PMCs, direct burning and macroscale cone calorimeter (MCC, Fire Testing Technology, UK) were performed. In brief, the same size (10 × 10 mm) of samples were cut from PMC membranes and ignited with a portable gas lighter in a UL-test chamber, once it caught up fires, the ignitor was removed immediately and the burning phenomenon was recorded by photos. Meanwhile, MCC was used to understand the combustion behavior of PMC membranes. The samples ($\sim 5 \text{ mg}$) were heated from 100 to 700°C in the pyrolysis zone with a heating rate of 1°C s⁻¹, all experiments were done in quadruplicates. The heat release rate (HRR) was obtained from the oxygen depletion measurements in W g⁻¹.

3. Result and Discussion

The phase structure of PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50 electrolytes was characterized by XRD as shown in Fig. 2a. The specific characteristic peaks of PEO, HKUST-1, and LLZTO diffractograms can be found in the patterns of PMC without impurity peaks, indicating that the

mild preparation process can efficiently maintain original structures. Compared to sharp and intense peaks at 19.2° , and 23.3° in 2θ of highly crystalline PEO samples, both PMC10 and PMC30 electrolytes show widened and weakened intensity, while the peaks are negligible in PMC50. The comparatively reduced intensities of peaks in the XRD pattern indicate the crystallization ability of PEO has been remarkably restricted with the increasing content of LLZTO. Fig. 2b offers the FTIR spectra for analyzing the inner molecular interaction of PMCs. Pure PEO shows a clear signal around 2871 cm^{-1} , attributed to the C-H stretching mode, and shifts to $2881\text{-}2884\text{ cm}^{-1}$ after the incorporation of MOF and LLZTO into PEO electrolytes. Furthermore, the semicrystalline phase of PEO is confirmed by the existence of a triplet peak of C-O-C stretching[34, 35], found at 1144 , 1091 , and 1058 cm^{-1} vibrations. Compared with pure PEO, PMC electrolytes show a slight shift and broader peaks at 1188 , 1096 , and 1055 cm^{-1} , confirming the subtle alteration of chemical structure. Meanwhile, two functional groups (1647 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 726 cm^{-1} (C-H)) of HKUST-1 appear and the characteristic absorption peaks at 862 and 1417 cm^{-1} occur at the spectrum of LLZTO.

Fig. 2. (a) XRD diffraction patterns and (b) FTIR spectra of PMCs. (c) Cross-sectional and (d, e) top-view SEM images of PMC50 CSSE.

Interfacial compatibility and stability are crucial factors affecting the electrochemical performance of solid electrolytes. As shown in SEM images of PMC50 (Fig. 2c), a distinct double-layer structure with a total thickness of $\sim 150 \mu\text{m}$ is obtained with a smooth upper layer of “CIP” structure thickened in $\sim 90 \mu\text{m}$ and a bottom layer of “PIC” structure thickened in $\sim 60 \mu\text{m}$. This unique structure is created by the gravity effect of LLZTO during the drying procedure and is verified by the EDS elemental mapping as shown in Fig. S1. Furthermore, Fig. 2d and 2e depict the surface topographies of two layers, the CIP layer shows uniformly dispersed island crystalline regions with a feature size of $\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$, which are generated due to the volatilization of solvents[36], while the PIC layer has a relative rough micrograph and is similar to the morphology of the pristine LLZTO (Fig. S2a). Meanwhile, the distribution of layers can be adjusted by controlling the feeding ratio of polymers and ceramics. For example, PMC10 in Fig. S2b displays a CIP-dominated bilayer interface. Contrary to images of PMCs, in Fig. S2c, PEO SPE ($\text{Li}^+ : \text{EO} = 1:15$) shows obvious

semi-crystalline spherulite morphologies, which can be suppressed to some extent by the plasticizer effect of MOF nanoparticles, as the reduced and smaller spheres in Fig. S2d shown.

Fig. 3. (a) DSC, (b) TGA thermograms, (c) $\tan \delta$ versus temperature plots, and (d) stress-strain curves of PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50.

DSC test was performed to analyze the thermal-induced phase-change behavior of PMC composite electrolytes, such as glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m), degree of crystallinity (χ_c), and enthalpy value (ΔH_m). As shown in Fig. 3a and S3a, an endothermic peak corresponding to T_m of the crystalline state is found at 64.4°C in the curve of pure PEO, while the T_m of PMC decreases significantly to ~50°C and the endothermic area experiences a notable reduction. The shift of T_m value towards lower temperature symbolizes the increase of amorphous phases, which can be verified by χ_c calculated following Eq. (1). In comparison to the crystallinity of 66.0% of pure PEO, after dispersed with different contents of additives, the χ_c of PMCs reduce to 15.2%, 13.7%, and 5.4%, respectively. Meantime, the moderate enhancement in T_g of PMC10,

PMC30, and PMC50 is attributed to the coordination effects between additives and polyether chains, data details are given in Table S1. Subsequently, the thermal stability of PMCs was accessed by the TGA test. As shown in Fig. 3b, the slight weight loss (less than 3%) below 100°C is caused by the evaporation of trace moisture, and PMCs undergo a multi-stage decomposition with a major weight loss occurs between 350-450°C, which is contributed by the decomposition of PEO and HKUST-1. The amounts of residue 10.9%, 26.8%, and 54.8% at 800°C are consistent with feeding ratios, whereas the single-modified SPEs (PM and PC10) in Fig. S3b show finite enhancement. PMCs exhibit improved thermal stability compared to single-modified solid electrolytes, which results from the synergistic influence of the obstruction effect of MOF and the incombustible nature of ceramics.

Since electrolytes act as the bridge connecting two electrodes, proper mechanical strength is crucial to maintain an intact shape during their lifespan[37]. Ceramics consist of dense pellets with high interfacial resistance and typically are difficult to be processed owing to their rigid nature[38]. Conversely, PEO, as a conventional thermoplastic polymer, can be easily fabricated into desired shapes, but the soft nature permits notorious dendrite growth which may induce internal short circuits[39]. PMCs combine the soft interface of PEO and the hard nature of LLZTO, the corresponding uniaxial tensile stress-strain behavior was investigated with DMA. The dependency of $\tan \delta$ with temperature is obtained from the oscillatory tension deformation and shown in Fig. 3c, which is considered as the mechanical damping factor related to molecular movements[40]. As the temperature increases from -80 to 60°C at a speed of 3°C min⁻¹, PMCs undergo three periods progressively. During stage I, PMCs are in the glassy region, the polymer chains are hard and brittle; Stage II is the transition region, where the segmental movement becomes more flexible; Stage III is the rubbery plateau region, where polymer chains exhibit a large elastic

deformation[41]. T_g shows a decreasing trend with LLZTO content increased, which conforms to the DSC results listed in Table S1. PMC50 exhibits the highest storage modulus (E') in the glass state, benefiting from the contribution of LLZTO (Fig. S3c and S3d). As seen in Fig. 3d, all samples do not fracture after 400% elongation until limited by the maximum stroke of machine, confirming the excellent deformability of PMCs. Young's modulus, as an important index commonly used to evaluate the stiffness of materials[42], is calculated according to Eq. (2). Owing to the combination of the stiffness from LLZTO and the toughness from polymers with excellent flexibility, Young's modulus of PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50 present 3.1, 4.4, and 5.2 MPa, respectively, which can effectively withstand mechanical stresses, maintain the structural integrity, and meet the mechanical needs of LIBs in the long-term usage, whereas the PEO SPE shows a dissatisfied value of 1.0 MPa and fractures after reaching the maximum strain of 240% (Fig. S4).

Fig. 4. Monitoring pictures of PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50 burning for 1 s, 5 s, and 10 s.

PMCs combine the flame-retardant HKUST-1 and the nonflammable ceramic, the fire safety is hoped to present alleviated combustion behaviors compared to PEO SPE. Hence, the direct burning experiment is performed to track the burning details of PMCs, including burning time, extinguishing time, fire severity as well as residues. Fig. 4 records the burning moments for 1 s, 5 s, and 10 s, respectively. Once ignited, the igniter is immediately retracted and the timing is started. PEO SPE burns most violently with melt dripping phenomenon and no residue remains, while PM demonstrates a notably subdued burning behavior, though still showing a dripping phenomenon. In contrast, PMCs burn less vigorously and leave residues after extinguishing. Among them, PMC50 exhibits the best flame retardancy and maintains its shape by forming a highly condensed char layer as revealed by Fig. S5, which can cover the substrate surface to suppress heat and mass transfer. PMC10 has moderate flame retardancy due to its low ceramic amount. Furtherly, MCC is used to measure the released heat from combustible materials as a standard method, which allows a comprehensive assessment of safety concerns including HRC, peak heat release rate (pHRR), total heat release (THR) values, and temperature of peak heat release rate (T_{\max})[43]. As summarized in Table 2, the incorporation of HKUST-1 and LLZTO leads to a notable suppression of heat production and a reduced propensity for heat release under elevated temperatures. Compares to PEO SPE, HRC values of PM and PC10 decrease significantly from $374 \text{ J g}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ to $260 \text{ J g}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $311 \text{ J g}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively, where PMC10 shows a decrease of 33.4% in comparison with PEO electrolytes. Meanwhile, pHRR reduce from 355 W g^{-1} to 250 W g^{-1} and 295 W g^{-1} for PM and PC10, respectively. Additionally, the T_{\max} and THR of PMCs are remarkably more pronounced decreasing trend due to the synergistic effect of MOFs and LLZTO, for instance, the THR of PMC50 drops to 10.8 kJ g^{-1} , while the THR of PEO membranes is as high as 16 kJ g^{-1} , signifies the improved thermal stability of the PMCs. The utilization of fire-safer PMC

electrolytes holds great potential in preventing catastrophic incidents and promoting the widespread adoption of safer energy storage technologies.

Table 2 MCC test results of PEO, PC10, PM, PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50 membranes.

<i>Samples</i>	<i>HRC</i> ($J g^{-1} K^{-1}$)	<i>pHRR</i> ($W g^{-1}$)	<i>T_{max}</i> ($^{\circ}C$)	<i>THR</i> ($kJ g^{-1}$)
<i>PEO</i>	374	355	417	16.0
<i>PC10</i>	260	250	404	15.5
<i>PM</i>	311	295	407	16.3
<i>PMC10</i>	249	237	404	15.9
<i>PMC30</i>	209	197	406	13.9
<i>PMC50</i>	183	174	386	10.8

To further investigate the compatibility of PMCs, the electrochemical window (EW) was tested by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) method from 2.0 to 5.5 V with a sweep rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹ at 50°C. Fig. 5a compares the potential stability of PMCs with control groups, all electrolytes display a stable platform high to ~4.5 V, which can guarantee the voltage scope required for LFP (~3.8 V vs Li/Li⁺). Furthermore, as revealed in the inserted graph, the currents of PMCs are lower than control groups under high voltage (above 4.5 V), which may result from the hampered oxidation and decomposition of PEO after fillers incorporation[44, 45]. Afterward, EIS measurements were conducted to figure out the influence of additives on Li⁺ conduction. Fig. 5b illustrates the variation of ionic conductivity of PMC10 within a wide temperature range, the resistance decreases sharply as the temperature rises (388 Ω at 30°C), and PMC10 shows an optimal ionic conductivity of $2.33 \times 10^{-4} S cm^{-1}$ at 50°C. By contrast, in Fig. 5c, PEO SPE possesses a high interface impedance of 1850 Ω at 30°C and exhibits an ionic conductivity of

$6.38 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 50°C . This remarkable improvement in conductive ability is a result of the collaborative contribution of both MOF and LLZTO additives. As manifested in Fig. S6a and S6b, PM and PC10 show smaller resistance of $744 \ \Omega$ and $1009 \ \Omega$ at 30°C and higher ionic conductivity compared to unmodified PEO electrolytes. In addition, Fig. 5d gives the relevant Arrhenius plots of PMCs, where PMC10 achieves the highest ionic conductivity among all CSSEs. When the ceramic content is lower than the percolation threshold, the “CIP” structure dominates the transport of Li^+ by the polymer segmental movement, which can well explain the reason for the slope change observed around 50°C in the nonlinear plot. Close to T_m , the increased polymeric mobility promotes easier ionic conduction, the activation energy of PMC10 is 0.32 eV based on Arrhenius relation calculation, which is reduced notably compared to the activation energy of 1.06 eV below 50°C .

Fig. 5. (a) Linear sweep voltammetry curves of electrolyte membranes at 50°C (the inset is an enlarged view from 4.5 to 5.0 V). Nyquist plots of (b) PMC10 and (c) PEO at various temperatures from RT to 80°C, and (d) temperature dependence of ionic conductivity of PMC electrolytes.

Fig. 6. (a) Lithium plating/stripping galvanostatic cycles of Li|PMC10|Li cell at a current density of 0.2 mA cm⁻², (b) activation process of LFP|PMC10|Li cell, (c) cyclic voltammogram of LFP|PMC10|Li cell at a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹, (d) rate performances of LFP|PMC|Li cells at serial current rates, and (e) cycling performance of LFP|PMC|Li cells at 0.1 C, all tests were performed at 50°C.

The contact wettability and stability between solid electrolyte and lithium metal, as well as the interfacial stability during lithium intercalation/extraction, are important evaluation parameters

for the realization of high specific energy lithium batteries exceeding 350 Wh kg^{-1} . Meanwhile, the thermal runaway of Li batteries typically begins with the failure and decomposition of the solid electrolyte interface (SEI)[46]. Lithium stripping and plating experiments are performed based on symmetric Li cells to analyze the interfacial compatibility of PMCs against Li metals. As shown in Fig. 6a, at a constant current density of 0.2 mA cm^{-2} , the potential change of PMC10 is negligible during the whole cycle of 900 hours, indicating that its interface is moderately stable at such a high current density. On the contrary, PEO SPE and PMC30 experience internal short circuits and manifest continuous potential fluctuations after 50 hours at the same current density, the sudden drop in resistance implies battery failure induced by lithium dendrite growth (Fig. S7a and S7b). Nevertheless, after the current density reduces to 0.1 mA cm^{-2} , PMC30 and PMC50 can deliver a stable plating/stripping behavior to 900 hours as shown in Fig. S8a and S8b.

LFP is chosen as cathode since it has been accepted as the most stable cathodic material during the thermal runaway process, which is ascribed to the strong bond of octahedral $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ structure[47]. As shown in Fig. 6b, PMC10 first undergoes several activation cycles accompanied by reduced voltage polarization and increased capacity density. At the 8th cycle, a reversible capacity density of 168.5 Ah kg^{-1} is achieved with an overpotential of $\sim 0.1 \text{ V}$. In Fig. 6c, cyclic voltammetry (CV) test was conducted between 2.5 to 4.0 V. In the initial cycle, two oxidation and reduction peaks relating to the intercalation/deintercalation of Li^+ from/into the cathode appear at ~ 3.65 and $\sim 3.23 \text{ V}$, respectively. In the following cycles, the current increase steadily and the reduction peaks shift to $\sim 3.18 \text{ V}$, implying the decreasing internal polarization and a stabilizing contact interface. The capacity performance of PMCs at various cycling rates at 50°C are presented in Fig. 6d. In comparison with PEO SPE showing an inevitable capacity decline trend under high currents, PMCs show more stable capacity retentions with steady coulombic efficiencies, where

PMC10 shows highest capacity density, which mainly benefits from its excellent ionic conductivity and stable interface. The galvanostatic cycling performance of LFP|PMC|Li batteries at 0.1 C rate are presented in Fig. 6e, all cells ran 10 activation cycles in advance to achieve their stable capacity. Both PMC10 and PMC30 show excellent cycling behavior with high coulombic efficiencies after 400 cycles, whereas the capacity density of PMC50 decline inevitably after 80 cycles. The initial specific capacities of PMC10 and PMC30 are 158.5 and 147.9 Ah kg⁻¹, respectively, and then drop to 127.3, and 105.8 Ah kg⁻¹ after 200 cycles, with capacity retention efficiencies of 80.3% and 71.5%, respectively. The separate charge/discharge profiles are recorded in Fig. S9a and S9b, where PMC10 keeps a discharging capacity of 105.5 Ah kg⁻¹ after 500 cycles, whereas the counterpart of PMC30 maintains 87.0 Ah kg⁻¹, demonstrating PMC10 possesses better electrochemical properties. As shown in Fig. S9c and S9d, PMC50 displays inhomogeneous surfaces and contains large areas of roughness after disassembling the batteries, however, the good contact compatibility of PMC10 and PMC30 makes it difficult to strip off.

4. Conclusion

To improve the fire safety performance of the CSSEs while ensuring excellent electrochemical performance in LIBs, HKUST-1 and LLZTO with different content ratios were added to the PEO substrate to obtain PMC10, PMC30, and PMC50 CSSEs with a uniform thickness of ~150 μm. Due to the gravitational effect of ceramic particles, a hierarchical CIP-PIC structure is formed. PMCs showed restrained crystallization ability, improved thermal stability, and reinforced mechanical properties, which surpassed conventional PEO SPE from diverse differential requirements. As a result, exceptional electrochemical compatibility (EW to ~4.5 V) and satisfactory ionic conduction (PMC10, 2.33×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ at 50°C) were achieved. Notably, PMC10 exhibited excellent interfacial stability and cycle performance with a stable

plating/stripping behavior for 900 hours at a current density of 0.2 mA cm^{-1} , a discharge capacity density of 158.5 Ah kg^{-1} , and a capacity retention of 80.3% after 200 cycles. This work contributes to the advancement of safer energy storage technologies and paves the way for the widespread adoption of CSSEs in fire-resistant LIBs.

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Credit author statement

Mingyang Zhang: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Writing original draft; Yusuf: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology; De-Yi Wang: Writing review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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